

The Teaching and Learning of Communication Skills in Secondary Schools Through Information Communication Technology

Author(s), OLOWOYEYE, Cyril Abioye Charles

Abstract:

The mastery of communication skills is the goal of the literacy drive advocated by the National Policy on Education. The advent of information communication technology is a modern invention geared towards accelerating effective teaching and learning processes if properly harnessed by educational institutions. The pedagogic object of utilizing ICT to inculcate language and communication skills is the main preoccupation of this paper. Likewise, the challenges: possibilities and problems of ICT to language teachers and learners are discussed.

Keywords: Teaching, Learning, Communication skills, ICT,

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About Author

Author(s):

OLOWOYEYE, Cyril Abioye Charles

Department of Language and Linguistics,
School of Multidisciplinary Studies,
Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology,
Ikere – Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Communication, in this twenty-first century, has transcended the threshold of common parlance culminating into the present sophisticated information communication technologies. The transmission of messages, today through the ICT has pushed back the frontiers of science thereby making the world a global village. And to keep pace with this technological advancement, secondary students in particular need to be computer literate. Luther, (2022) posited that ICT motivates both teachers and learners thereby making the learning process tremendously enjoyable. Likewise, interactive computer networking allows students to test the result of learning without the risk of being punished for any mistake. Researchers have affirmed that ICT plays a vital role in the teaching/learning of the English language in schools, colleges and universities (Hossain, 2021). Information Communication Technology (ICT) has become a household term globally and has brought radical changes in the way people live, learn and work. It has become a veritable tool in education and training by linking students with information technology and improving innovations for teachers. ICTs are potentially powerful enabling tool for educational advancement and reform, when used appropriately; it will improve teaching and learning processes.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) are electronic technologies used for information storage and retrieval. Development is partly determined by the ability to establish a synergistic interaction between technological innovation and human values. The rapid rate at which ICTs have evolved since the mid 20th century, the convergence and pervasiveness of ICTs, give them a strong role in development and globalization (Danbaba, et al., 2022). ICTs have a significant impact on all areas of human activity . The field of education has been affected by ICTs, which have undoubtedly affected teaching, learning, and research (Zenda, & Dlamini, 2022). A great deal of research has proven the benefits to the quality of education (Chen, & 2021). ICTs have the potential to accelerate, enrich, and deepen skills, to motivate and engage students, to help relate school experience to work practices, create economic viability for tomorrow's workers, as well as strengthening teaching and helping schools change (Borah, & Verma, 2022).

In a rapidly changing world, basic education is essential for an individual be able to access and apply information. Such ability must find include ICTs in the global village. The Economic Commission for Africa has indicated that the ability to access and use information is no longer a luxury, but a necessity for development. Unfortunately, many developing counties, especially in Africa, are still low in ICT application and use (Yusuf, & Iyabo, 2022). This paper focuses on ICT application in Nigerian secondary schools. It particularly dwells on the importance of ICT and the causes of low levels of ICT application in Nigerian secondary schools. Recommendations for improvement are offered.

This was viewed as a major tool for building knowledgeable societies (UNESCO, 2013). In Nigeria, certain Government educational policies are aimed at enforcing this technological innovation on schools. This makes access to information through technology to grow exponentially. Business Education cannot remain a mere subject, rather it should be an

innovative subject and schools need to improve in teaching and learning processes through the use of ICT. Therefore, the acquisition of ICT knowledge and skills can make it plausible learning over the lifetime (Senkbeil, 2022).

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) refers to all kinds of electronic system that are used for broadcasting, telecommunications and all forms of computer-mediated communications. It involves the use of online self-learning packages, interactive CDs chips, satellites, radio, optics fiber technology, tele-presence systems and all types of computer hardware or software (Sofroniou, 2018). Therefore, Information Technology (IT) is the use of computer systems and telecommunication equipment in information processing. It is made up of three basic components which are; electronic processing using the computer, transmission of information using telecommunication equipment and dissemination of information in multimedia. Information Communication Technology (ICT) has become integral part of teaching and learning in schools as it provides opportunities for both teachers and students to learn how to operate in an information and technology age for better understanding of Education. However, literature shows that although educators appear to acknowledge the value of ICT, difficulties continue to be encountered in adopting and integrating such technologies (Koh, et al., 2022).

Although many teachers are comfortable with the emergence of technology in general, the state of ICT facilities both software and hardware, and the lack of adequate ICT text books affect effective teaching and learning. Additionally, the problem of information technology illiteracy was a serious one among teachers and students. That is, many teachers and students did not have basic computer appreciation skills and noted that the problem was a hindrance to efforts at achieving the use of ICT for educational purposes in schools. The problem of this study is to determine the extent of the use of ICT in teaching and learning in Nigeria (Koh et al., 2022).

Language Teaching and Learning

Language has been defined in various ways by different linguists and language specialists. Bohn et al., (2022) simply defined language as a set of signals by which we communicate. This presupposes passing information from one person to the other. Olowoyeye (2004) corroborated asserted that language is used by human beings as means of communication, interaction and expression of thoughts, ideas and so on. ICT has succeeded in making language more versatile in the exchange and transmission of feelings, facts and messages. Teaching has been defined in several ways. Firstly, perceived teaching as a profession; secondly as a cluster of activities, we engage in during some specific period. And thirdly as an act of a particular kind, i.e. movement of the body, or parts of the body, talking, pausing, explaining, reading, etc. (Robert, 2022). In a clearer and measurable term, Soko, (2022) postulated that effective teaching and learning is geared towards producing active, literate and numerate persons who can read and write with required understanding and communicate without any ambiguity. Teaching is also an all-purpose profession that stimulates the development of the mental, physical and emotional power of students. When

properly done, this will produce educated citizens who would be sensitive and equipped with the imaginative resourcefulness to promote sound health, equality, peaceful coexistence, environmental management and a democratic process (Oyekan, 1994). Teaching performs such roles as: informing and explaining stimulating, directing, guiding and administering identifying what learn, identifying learning problems, evaluating, reporting, and recording-(Leiber, 2022).). Teaching is also pedestalled on some sound principles such as: Clear objectives, Pupil's readiness, Previous experience, Individual differences and Teaching should be systematic, proceeding from the known to the unknown.

Summarily, language, according to Hamidu (2004) is the study of the art of language which in effect involves the understanding of the importance of language as a vehicle of communication. Learning can be perceived as the acquisition of new knowledge, ideas, skills, values and experiences which enable the individual to modify or alter his actions. It also involves the utilization of the newly acquired knowledge or experience. Learning brings about permanent changes in the learner. Oyekan (1994), defined learning as a gradual change in behaviour that ought to be frequently practised and reinforced to prevent its extinction. It is perceived as a sort of biological adaptation as it occurs when the pupil adjusts to cope with the conditions of the educational environment and dynamic society.

Language learning is a process that is brought about in a classroom setting where | subject matter is selected, graded and activities are organized to promote the use of the language. The rules of the language are also internalized through the process of learning in the instructional setting (Seweje, 2006).

Language and Communication Skills

Afe, et al (2004) defined communication as the act of passing across information, news, or ideas to another person. In the same vein, Olowoyeye (2004) opined that it is the art of sharing, imparting and transmitting information with the sole aim of impacting behaviour, attitude and action.

The communication skills are broadly categorized into four namely: (a) listening (b) speaking (c) reading and (d) writing. These skills can be further grouped into groups according to their relatedness. They are:

- a. Receptive skills i.e. listening and reading skills.
- b. Expressive or productive skills i.e. speaking and writing.

Hybel and Weaver II (2001) asserted that communication is transactional which involves not only the physical act of communicating but also a psychological act.

Information Communication Technologies

The status of ICT in Nigeria today is highly enhanced due to its diversified usages. The use of computers and electronic communication gadgets now permeate various sectors such as education, banking, commerce, banking, governance, administration, etc. The use of the electronic machine in the ongoing voters' registration is an example of the ICT drive. But this is not to say that a great percentage of Nigerian students are not ICT compliant. According to Seweje (2006) despite the copious exposure through GST courses in computers more than 80% of Nigerian undergraduates and graduates alike are unable to adequately utilize the

computer. And more than 90% by a conservative estimate of the Nigerian secondary school pupils are unable to use the computer. While at the primary school level, less than 5% of the total population is computer literate.

In this information age, the pervasive impact of ICT on nearly all ramifications of human endeavours cannot be overemphasized. This is evinced in Oliver et al (1992) definition of ICT as the technology which supports activities that involve the creation, storage, manipulation and communication of information together with their related methods, management and applications. ICT also encompasses all forms of computer-mediated communication. These are well expatiated in Pearson et al (2003) as:

a. Electronic Mail (e-mail): makes use of an internet network to send messages to person(s) connected to the network.

b. Instant Messaging (IM): is a text-based form of synchronous communication which allows users to connect two computers near the internet and enable a conversation between the computers. This is referred to as an internet chat. This can also make multiple users log on and interact with other users via the internet.

c. Bulletin Board System (BBS): is the use of a text-based asynchronous communication tool that allows users to pass across information to a large number of people.

d. Audio-Video Conferencing: is the use of the network to connect two or more multimedia-capable computers for live, interactive conversation using visual-auditory channels of communication.

e. Multi-User (MUDS): are web-based virtual worlds where the participant can interact and engage in fantasy role-playing, This is an emerging realm of entertainment.

f. E-Learning: According to Sloman (2001), this is the electronic connection of a dispersed group of learners and individualised curricula that can deliver instant learning on a global basis.

ICT and Secondary School English Language Curriculum

The National Curriculum was evolved to enhance the viability and fruition of the National Policy which according to the English Language a place of prominence. Section 4:19 (6a) of the policy placed the English Language, as the first of the six are subjects. Likewise, the national curriculum for the junior and senior secondary schools embodied content materials on (1) vocabulary development (2) comprehension: listening and reading (3) structures (4) spoken English (5) writing and (6) literature; (NERC, 1985).

1. According to Fatodu (1995), the criteria for the selection of these content materials are to inculcate in the student, not only linguistic and communicative competence but also the ability to appreciate, with a critical sense, literacy materials in English.

The curriculum also expressly stated its objectives as: *...to promote systematic development of both the language skills and the literacy knowledge that are considered essential for effective use of English in oral and written communication as well as learning other subjects in the curriculum".*

The application of ICT can help foster the teaching and learning of these skills. According to Fakeye and Aturamu (2006) such instructional materials as slide projector, video camera and

cassette slides, multimedia laboratory, audio-visual aids, software and hardware consumables etc, can enhance learning tremendously.

Application of ICT on Communication Skills Teaching and Learning

ICT is permeating the learning environment at a very rapid rate. There are several attempts to reposition teaching and learning in line with the operational paradigm of ICT. The teaching-learning process is now being redesigned not only to accommodate but to reflect ICT in all its ramifications; Seweje (2006). Students can learn language skills pleurably. This is made possible with the use of computers and laptops. Examples include:

a. Letter fun PC designed by Vtech christened Little Smart. It can be used to enhance the sounds produced by different animals that are matched with the animal when the appropriate keys are pressed. Spelling drills can be taught. The fun PC avails the little child the means of learning sounds of a letter (Oral-Aural skills) finding missing letters (spelling) etc.

b. The Vtech Pre-computer PC is well designed to teach and enhance the learning of spelling, word processing, word games, logic games etc. The secondary school pupil can easily learn on his own the language skills with fun.

c. Computer Games/VCD—there are various types of computer VCD. Some are quite educative and can be adapted by teachers and students alike in the teaching and learning of language skills.

This is corroborated by Seweje (2006) who outlined five (5) directing a language user could take to teach the language and communication skills. They are:

1. Commercial Software (CD-ROMs)—there are several language CD-ROMs and diskettes available in the market. Teachers should select the relevant available ones.
2. World Wide Web (www)—the www is quite an invaluable resource for language teachers and learners. Students can be aided to find sites that explain the various language skills.
3. The e-mail system. This can enable students to communicate with other teachers and learners of language at a very cheap rate when they operate their e-mail addresses.
4. Presentation Software includes PowerPoint, presentations which can be used to make slides accompany lectures and presentations as well as to stimulate conversation.
5. Authoring Software—this software allows teachers to create exercises, language drills to create exercises, language drills and activities in the multimedia laboratory.

Likewise, the internet can help networking with many computers throughout the world. These are: **LAN**—Local Area Network

VAN—Wide Area Network

The LAN can be used in a locality like a school setting. Teaching can be conducted with learners hooked to the network in active participation. Also, the WAN is used to connect computers over a wide geographical area. It can even cover countries and continents. This can be very appropriate in integrating skills to students that are hooked to this network. Heathcote (2000) listed, among others, the advantages of LAN and WAN in the teaching of communication skills:

- a. It allows the sharing of resources such as disk storage, printers, image scanners modems (Modulator/Demodulator=MODEM) and central servers. These can be used with relevant packages to inculcate the skills.
- b. It allows electronic mail (e-mail) to be sent between users. This will enhance the exchange of responses to exercises and assignments between teachers and students.
- c. It allows sharing of information held in disk drives accessible by all users. This enhances the transmission of instructions and assignments from teachers to learners. It allows the connection of different types of computers which can communicate with each other; etc.

The Challenges of ICT to Language Teachers and Learners

In this paper, the challenge is used to mean:

- a. the possibilities of ICT,
- b. the problems to be tackled in the use of ICT.

a. The Challenges (Possibilities) of ICT

Dwyer et al (1990) discovered that in a learning environment supported by ICT, teachers:

- are less predominant, students are more active,
- expect more from students;
- can present more complex materials;
- can effectively meet the needs of the individual students;
- are more willing to experiment;
- are more open to multiple perspectives on problems;
- feel more professional because they help people learn rather than dispense information,

b. Challenges (Problems to be tackled) of ICT

It is not an overstatement that more than 90% of teachers and lecturers of language are not ICT compliant. This was corroborated by Seweje (2006) as enforcement. But this challenge can be confronted.

1. Teachers should strive to be ICT compliant by being involved.
2. They must broaden their horizon on the use of ICT. Stefansdotir (2001) observed that a teacher has to understand that ICT is to be used as a tool. Therefore, usage in the classroom calls for a level of knowledge of the technology. ,
- 3 Teachers should develop procedures to solve problems and inculcate relevant skills.
4. Be adept in the use of computer programs including drills, tutorials, simulation, information retrieval, and data management.

Conclusion

The advent of ICT has extended the frontiers of knowledge and enriched the teaching and learning process. The language teachers could, with the use of ICT, disseminate knowledge, skills, information better. It is therefore highly imperative that 'ge and communication teachers be up-to-date in the use of ICT for better performance. Learners as well have to be well-groomed in the use of ICT. The use of ICT both by the teachers and learners could be

very costly. Therefore, the government will need to come to their aid. This could be in form of grants, provision of the appropriate ICT tools, etc.

References

- Bohn, M., Liebal, K., Oña, L., & Tessler, M. H. (2022). Great ape communication as contextual social inference: a computational modelling perspective. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, 377(1859), 20210096.
- Borah, J., & Verma, V. (2022). ICT: A game changer in modern education.
- Chen, C. H., & Tsai, C. C. (2021). In-service teachers' conceptions of mobile technology-integrated instruction: Tendency towards student-centered learning. *Computers & Education*, 170, 104224.
- Companies Moran, C. and Selte, C. L. (1999). Teaching English across the Technology/Wealth gap. Trends and Issues in Secondary School English—2001 (Ed)
- Danbaba, S. A., Titus, T. N., & Panshak, T. N. (2022). Assessing Information Dissemination Channels as Valuable Tools for Educational Development in Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1), 129-132.
- David, M. F. B., Davis, M. H., Harden, R. M., Howie, P. W., Ker, J., & Pippard, M. J. (2001). AMEE Medical Education Guide No. 24: Portfolios as a method of student assessment. *Medical teacher*, 23(6), 535-551.
- Fakeye A. O. and Aturamu, O. O. (2006). Instructional Materials and Language Teaching in a Technological World. Book of Proceedings of the First National Conference on Language Teaching in a Technological World held between 25th and 28th April 2006. San-Ayo Printer-83 – 88
- Fatodu, C. A. (1995). English Language Teaching at the Secondary School (A Problem of Transition from the Primary School). *African Journal of Information Technology (AJI)*, 1(2), 126-130
- Federal Republic of Nigeria(1981). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos Government
- Hossain, M. M. (2021). English language teaching through virtual classroom during COVID-19 lockdown in Bangladesh: challenges and propositions. *Journal of English Education and Teaching*, 5(1), 41-60.
- Hybel S. and Weaver 11 R. (2001). *Communicating Effectively* 6th Edition New York: McGraw Hill

- Koh, K. T., Tan, L. Q. W., Camiré, M., Paculdar, M. A. A., & Chua, W. G. A. (2022). Teachers' and students' perceptions of factors influencing the adoption of information and communications technology in physical education in Singapore schools. *European Physical Education Review*, 28(1), 100-119.
- Leiber, T. (2022). Justifying, contextualising and operationalising performance indicators of learning and teaching: the role of theories and practice of learning and teaching. *Quality in Higher Education*, 28(1), 120-140.
- Luther, V. L. (2022). The Impacts of Self-Efficacy and Intrinsic Motivation: Mentoring Students to Be Motivated Readers. *The Language and Literacy Spectrum*, 32(1), 2.
- National Teachers Institute (1990). Education Cycle 1. Kaduna: National Teachers Institute
- Oliver, E. C., R. J. Chapman, C. S. French, (1992). *Data Processing and Information Technology*. London: DP Publications Ltd.
- Olowoyeye, C. A. (2004). *Use of English for Professionals*, Akure; J. V. Educational
- Oyekan, S. O. (1994). Fundamentals of Education, in W. Osisanwo (Ed) *Education for Nigeria Certificate in Education*. Ondo: Adeyemi College of Education Textbook Development Board, 1 -58
- Oyekan, S. O. (2000). *Foundation of Teacher Education*. Okitipupa: Ebunola Printers
- Pearson, J. C., Nelson, P. E., Titsworth, S. and L. Harter (2003). Human Communication New York: McGraw-Hill Companies Inc.
- Printer Heathcote, P. M. (2000). "A " Level ICT 2nd Edition. Great Britain: Northgate St. Publishers
- Robert, O. S. (2022). Language as a Medium for Bridging the Gap Between Philosophy, Media, and Development. In *Handbook of Research on Connecting Philosophy, Media, and Development in Developing Countries* (pp. 26-41). IGI Global.
- Senkbeil, M. (2022). ICT-related variables as predictors of ICT literacy beyond intelligence and prior achievement. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(3), 3595-3622.
- Seweje, E. O. (2006). *The Teaching of English as a Second Language*. Lagos: Dolphin Publisher
- Seweje, R. O. (2006): Imperatives of Information Technology (ICT) for Teachers. A Paper presented at the TRCN 2006 ICT Skill Acquisition Summits and Campaigns for Teachers' in Akure Zone held at the Pope John Paul Pastoral Centre, Ado-Ekiti from October 15-21, 2006

Sloman, M. (2001). *The E-Learning Revolution*. London: C1PD

Sofroniou, A. (2018). *Relational Databases and Distributed Systems*. Lulu. com.

Soko, Z. (2022). *Teaching strategies that can improve literacy levels among the lower primary school learners in selected government primary schools in Kitwe* (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Zambia). Teachers, Iceland: The Ak

Todd, L. (1993): *An Introduction to Linguistics* London: Longman Group Limited Stefansdottir, L.

Yusuf, S., & Iyabo, A. M. (2022). Adoption of Information and Communication Technology: a Strategy For Promoting Lecturers' Effectiveness in Nigerian Universities. *Journal Educatio FKIP UNMA*, 8(3), 786-799.

Zenda, R., & Dlamini, R. (2022). Examining factors that influence teachers to adopt information and Communication Technology in rural secondary schools: an empirical study. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-18.

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